

Design and Analysis of Microstrip Patch Array Antenna for 24 GHz Radar Sensors Application

¹Rahul Kumar, ²Dr. Bharti Chourasia

¹ME Scholar, ²Associate Professor & HOD

^{1&2}Department of Electronics & Communication,

^{1&2}RKDF Institute of Science & Technology, SRK University, Bhopal, India

Abstract: As a new type of microwave antenna, micro-strip antenna enjoys the various advantages over parabolic antenna: little section plane, light weight and low cost. It can be made into the structure corresponds with carries such as communication vehicles and so on. Yet the typical micro-strip antenna element is difficult to adapt the demands of satellite communication system in the different aspects like bandwidth, dual frequency and double polarization etc. This paper proposed microstrip patch array antenna for 24 GHz radar sensors application. CST microwave studio used for designing and simulation of antenna array. Proposed antenna achieves -29.01dB return loss at 24GHz resonant frequency, Bandwidth optimized 697.95 MHz and Gain is 13.36 dB.

Keywords: K-band, Microstrip, Antenna, Radar, Satellite, Array.

1. INTRODUCTION

The millimeter-wave antenna design aspect of the future 5G wireless systems. The study reviews the various millimeter-wave antennas for 5G radar sensors applications. Recent advances in mm-wave antenna are reported and design guidelines are discussed. In Radar Sensors for automotive applications are typically divided into two categories: (1) continuous-wave (CW) radar and (2) pulse radar. CW radar transmits and receives at the same time. The transmitter generates a continuous sinusoidal oscillation at frequency f_t which is radiated by the antenna. On reflection by a moving target, the transmitted signal is shifted via the Doppler effect by an amount f_d . It is also possible to measure range using a CW radar system by frequency modulation, or digital modulation techniques such as phase shift keying (PSK). A systematic variation of transmitted frequency or phase places a unique time stamp on the transmitted wave at every instant.

Figure 1: Basic structure of a microstrip patch antenna

An individual microstrip antenna consists of a patch of metal foil of various shapes (a patch antenna) on the surface of a PCB (printed circuit board), with a metal foil ground plane on the other side of the board. Most microstrip antennas consist of multiple patches in a two-dimensional array. In modern days, Microstrip patch antennas become more popular because of its fascinating features such as low cost, light weight, low profile planar configuration which can be effortlessly made conformal to host surface.

2. BACKGROUND

H. Jin et al.,[2018] A small scale strip radio wire exhibit with low side-lobe is intended for 24GHz radar sensors right now. The proposed microstrip reception apparatus exhibit is sustained

by an arrangement feed organize which can diminish obstruction of feed arrange and acknowledge scaling down of radio wire on premise of fulfilling prerequisite of every component of receiving wire cluster energized by the inconsistent sufficiency. This work will detail plan of feed organize and the disengagement structure to advance radiation example of the reception apparatus exhibit. The reproduction results show the side-lobe level of the reception apparatus cluster is - 26.5dB.[1]

R. Tiwari, et al.,[2019] MIMO advancement has pulled in thought in remote correspondences, since it present gigantic augmentations in data throughput and association reach out without requiring extra transmission limit or transmit control, higher spooky viability and lessened obscuring, a few systems can be associated with improve the microstrip antenna move speed.[2]

R. Babulkar et al.,[2019] In wireless communication, more than one signals are transmitted in the channel by using the concept of Orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) which efficiently handles the inter symbol interference and utilizes the frequency and available bandwidth efficiently. Whereas for OFDM transmission technique is integrated with MIMO channel which contains multiple transmitter and receiver antenna at both ends.[3]

L. Zhang, et al.,[2018] Right now, voyaging wave opening exhibit on substrate integrated waveguide (SIW) for 24GHz traffic observing is planned. The receiving wire cluster accomplishes beam guiding through controlling the longitudinal opening separating. The primary beam focuses at a point of 20° and has the upside of scaling down, effectively manufactured and minimal effort. Mimicked result is confirmed right now.[4]

M. Straight, et al.,[2017] This work introduces the plan of a linearly captivated electronically reconfigurable transmitarray in K-band for beam directing applications. The transmitarray is a linear arrangement of five unit cells. Every unit cell gives a ceaseless stage tuning range of 360° which has been affirmed with numerical and trial results. The unit cells are shaped of numerous single layers of RF-overlay with varactor stacked fixes as tunable components and an opening for gap coupling. The layers are isolated by metal sheets gave gaps. The transmitarray is intended for a beam controlling range of $\pm 30^\circ$ which has been effectively shown at 24GHz.[5]

D. Henry, et al.,[2017] This work reports just because a long-range cross examination (> 50 meters) of remote and batteryless mugginess sensors consolidating a Van-Atta retrodirective cluster and a 3D beam filtering utilizing a 24GHz Recurrence Adjusted Consistent Wave radar. Van-Atta cross-polarization properties, just as the utilization of devoted factual estimators and Engineered Opening Radar technique permit the long-range estimation of the relative mugginess a good ways off of 58 meters. An estimation affectability of 0.2dB to 0.4dB per %RH was estimated as a linear variety of the proposed estimator with a standard blunder of ± 0.005 dB.[6]

Z. Gong, et al.,[2017] Right now, minimal planar 24GHz semi Yagi radio wire which utilizes a dipole driver is exhibited. The radio wire is intended for unmanned aerial vehicle(UAV) radar which requires reception apparatus' high coordination and scaling down. Semi Yagi radio wire is a smaller planar reception apparatus appropriate for millimeter-wave applications. Right now, one-dimensional radio wire exhibit is utilized to address the issue for scaling down. It drastically diminishes producing cost as well as takes out the requirement for consequent field disappointment control.[7]

L. Chen et al.,[2016] A 24GHz microstrip staged exhibit antennas with high pick up and low side-lobe is intended for automotive anticollision radar right now. The proposed microstrip receiving wire exhibit is nourished by an arrangement equal bolstering system which can lessen loss of feed organize and acknowledge scaling down of radio wire on premise of fulfilling necessity of every component of reception apparatus cluster energized by the inconsistent sufficiency. The reenactment results show the 8×12 radio wire exhibit has a bandwidth of 1.1GHz. The greatest examining edge is about $\pm 30^\circ$, and the base increase about 25dB. During the time spent checking point, the greatest beam width of E-plane and H-plane is 6° and 14.2°. What's more, the primary side-lobe level is - 18dB and - 19dB.[8]

3. PROPOSED DESIGN

The proposed research work is summarized is as follows-

- To propose a design of Microstrip patch antenna with array using finite ground plane for K-band.
- To evaluate the performance parameters.

- To improve in the performance parameters of proposed antenna designs such as: Reflection Coefficient or return loss, Bandwidth, Radiation Pattern, Gain, VSWR.
- To make comparison of the proposed designs with the existing designs for getting optimized design parameters.

Figure 2: Flow Chart

The flow chart work as following steps-

1. Calculation of antenna length, width through standard formula.
2. Make the ground, substrate and top level view through CST software.
3. Define waveguide port or feed patch
4. Simulation of proposed designed antenna.
5. Optimization of final design to see improvement in performance parameters.
6. Generate the results graph and calculation of parameters values.

Figure 3: Dimension of proposed antenna

Figure 3 is showing dimension of different component of proposed antenna. This dimension is calculated based on standard formulas and optimization. Therefore the dimension of antenna is (LxWxH) $30 \times 35.2 \times 1.67 \text{ mm}^3$. The proposed antenna is based on array pattern so the dimension of single component is $5.40 \times 3.93 \text{ mm}^2$. The length of feed patch is 17.67mm and width is 0.3mm. The substrate material which is using in proposed antenna is rogers lossy material.

Figure 4: (a) Side view (b) Bottom view of proposed antenna

Figure 4 (a) is showing side view of antenna; here it can be seen the feeding port which is also known as microwave port. Figure 4 (b) is showing bottom view of antenna, this is also known as ground structure. There are two types of ground structure, finite and defected ground structure. Proposed antenna is using finite ground structure.

4. SIMULATION AND RESULT GRAPHS

The antenna geometry is designed based on cartesian coordinate system which have x,y,z axis. Firstly make the basic microstrip patch antenna single elements then make the antenna array.

4.1 Return loss or S11

Return loss or S11 represents how much power is reflected from the antenna, and hence is known as the reflection coefficient. It indicates the proportion of radio waves arriving at the antenna input that are rejected as a ratio against those that are accepted.

Figure 5: Return loss

The obtained value of S₁₁ or return loss is -29.01 dB for 23.9 GHz or approx 24GHz resonant frequency, where antenna efficiency is higher.

4.2 Bandwidth

Figure 6: Bandwidth

The bandwidth of an antenna refers to the range of frequencies over which the antenna can operate correctly. The antenna's bandwidth is the number of Hz for which the antenna will exhibit an SWR less than 2:1. The bandwidth can also be described in terms of percentage of the center frequency of the band. For broadband antennas, the bandwidth is also expressed as a percentage of the frequency difference (upper minus lower) over the center frequency of the bandwidth. The bandwidth of proposed antenna is 697.95 MHz, (24.25 GHz – 23.55 GHz).

4.3 Voltage Standing Wave Ratio (VSWR)

Figure 7: VSWR

VSWR stands for Voltage Standing Wave Ratio, and is also referred to as Standing Wave Ratio (SWR). VSWR is a function of the reflection coefficient, which describes the power reflected from the antenna. A VSWR value lie between 1 to 2 is considered suitable for most antenna applications. The antenna can be described as having a good match. Therefore the VSWR value of proposed antenna is 1.0734.

4.4 Radiation Pattern

Figure 8: 3-D Radiation Pattern

A radiation pattern defines the variation of the power radiated by an antenna as a function of the direction away from the antenna. This power variation as a function of the arrival angle is observed in the antenna's far field. The far-field pattern of an antenna may be determined experimentally at an antenna range, or alternatively, the near-field pattern may be found using a near-field scanner, and the radiation pattern deduced from it by computation.[1] The far-field radiation pattern can also be calculated from the antenna shape by computer programs such as NEC. Other software, like HFSS, CST can also compute the near field.

Figure 9: Radiation Pattern- polar plot

The far field radiation pattern may be represented graphically as a plot of one of a number of related variables, including; the field strength at a constant (large) radius (an amplitude pattern or field pattern), the power per unit solid angle (power pattern) and the directive gain. Very often, only the relative amplitude is plotted, normalized either to the amplitude on the antenna boresight, or to the total radiated power. The plotted quantity may be shown on a linear scale, or in dB. The plot is typically represented as a three-dimensional graph (as at right), or as separate graphs in the vertical plane and horizontal plane. This is often known as a polar diagram.

Directivity is a fundamental antenna parameter. It is a measure of how 'directional' an antenna's radiation pattern is. An antenna that radiates equally in all directions would have effectively zero directionality, and the directivity of this type of antenna would be 1 (or 0 dB). The directivity of antenna is 14.15 dBi.

Antenna gain tells us the power transmitted by an antenna in a specific direction as compared to an isotropic antenna. This specification describes how strong a signal an antenna can send out or receive in a specified direction. The gain of antenna is 13.36 dB.

Table 1: Result summary of proposed Antenna

Sr. No.	Parameter	Optimized Band
1	S11 or Return Loss	-29.01 dB
2	Band Width	697.95 MHz
3	VSWR	1.0734
4	Resonant Frequency	23.9 GHz (Approx 24 GHz)
5	Gain	8.970dB
6	Radiated power	- 0.443 W
7	Power stimulated.	0.5 W
8	Y- Parameter	0.018
9	Z- Parameter	55.27
10	Directivity	14.15 dB
11	Gain	13.36 dB

Table 2: Comparison of proposed design result with previous design result

Sr No.	Parameter	Previous work	Proposed work
1	S11 or Return loss	-11.7 dB	-29.01 dB
2	Band Width	490 MHz	697.95 MHz
3	VSWR	1.18	1.0734
4	Resonant Frequency	23.9 GHz (Approx 24 GHz)	23.9 GHz (Approx 24 GHz)
5	Gain	13 dB	13.36 dB
6	Design type	Array (1X6)	Array (2X2)

Table 2 showing comparison of proposed antenna results with previous design result in terms of calculated parameters. Proposed antenna achieves -29.01dB return loss while previous -11.7 dB. Bandwidth optimized 697.95 MHz while previous 490 MHz and Gain is 13.36 dB while previous it is 13dB. Therefore above result shows that proposed antenna array gives significant improved result rather than the existing antenna design.

5. CONCLUSION

Microstrip The proposed design of single feed and single band characteristics on a Roger Substrate microstrip patch antenna array for radar and satellite applications have been investigated. Low profile microstrip fed rectangular patch antenna with single slot has been studied. Different parameters like VSWR values are 1.3, 0.79 and 1.54 for the respective frequencies 19.6 GHz, 22.8 GHz and 26.4 GHz for the proposed K antenna and the value of VSWR achieved is less than 1.5 in the desired operating bands likewise X antenna, the value of VSWR is 1.13 at 11GHz frequency. An array based, rectangular microstrip antenna is designed and simulated using CST simulation software. The simulation results are presented and discussed. Structure of proposed antenna is simple and compact in size of approx 30 X 35.2 X 1.6 mm³ the compact size of designed antenna makes it easy to be incorporated in small devices. Results show that the frequency bandwidth covers X band (18-27) GHz, at centre frequencies 24 GHz for VSWR less than 2, and S11 less than -10 dB. In above explained operating band it shows good impedance matching and bidirectional radiation patterns. Proposed antenna achieves -29.01dB return loss while previously shows -11.7 dB. Bandwidth optimized 697.95 MHz while previous bandwidth is 490 MHz and Gain is 13.36 dB while previous it is 13dB. Therefore it is clear that significant improvement achieved in this research work.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Jin, L. Zhu, X. Liu and G. Yang, "Design of a Microstrip Antenna Array with Low Side-Lobe for 24GHz Radar Sensors," 2018 International Conference on Microwave and Millimeter Wave Technology (ICMMT), Chengdu, 2018, pp. 1-3.
- [2] R. Tiwari, R. Sharma, R. Dubey "Review of Microstrip Patch Antenna Array and MIMO Antenna for Wireless Applications", International Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research, ISSN:2349-5162, Vol.6, Issue 5, page no.378-382, May-2019
- [3] R. Babulkar, "A Comprehensive Review on Channel Estimation Techniques in MIMO-OFDM", SMART MOVES JOURNAL IJOSCIENCE, vol. 5, no. 5, pp. 14-18, May 2019. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.24113/ijoscience.v5i5.204>.
- [4] L. Zhang, L. Li and H. Yi, "Design of a Traveling Wave Slot Array on Substrate Integrated Waveguide for 24GHz Traffic Monitoring," 2018 Cross Strait Quad-Regional Radio Science and Wireless Technology Conference (CSQRWC), Xuzhou, 2018, pp. 1-3.
- [5] M. Frank, R. Weigel and A. Koelpin, "A multilayer reconfigurable transmitarray in k-band for beam steering applications," 2017 International Conference on Electromagnetics in Advanced Applications (ICEAA), Verona, 2017, pp. 764-767.

- [6] D. Henry, J. G. D. Hester, H. Aubert, P. Pons and M. M. Tentzeris, "Long range wireless interrogation of passive humidity sensors using Van-Atta cross-polarization effect and 3D beam scanning analysis," *2017 IEEE MTT-S International Microwave Symposium (IMS)*, Honolulu, HI, 2017, pp. 816-819.
- [7] Z. Gong, S. Ge, T. Guo, Q. Zhang and Y. Chen, "A compact planar 24GHz quasi-Yagi antenna for unmanned aerial vehicle radar applications," *2017 IEEE International Conference on Computational Electromagnetics (ICCEM)*, Kumamoto, 2017, pp. 104-105.
- [8] L. Chen and M. Yan, "Design of 24GHz microstrip phased array antennas with low side-lobe," *2016 IEEE International Conference on Electronic Information and Communication Technology (ICEICT)*, Harbin, 2016, pp. 606-608.
- [9] G. F. Hamberger, A. Drexler, S. Trummer, U. Siart and T. F. Eibert, "A planar dual-polarized microstrip 1D-beamforming antenna array for the 24GHz ISM-band," *2016 10th European Conference on Antennas and Propagation (EuCAP)*, Davos, 2016, pp. 1-5.
- [10] S. Lan, Y. Xu, H. Chu, J. Qiu, Z. He and A. Denisov, "A novel 24GHz microstrip array module design for bioradars," *2015 International Symposium on Antennas and Propagation (ISAP)*, Hobart, TAS, 2015, pp. 1-3.
- [11] Yipan Zhou, Bing Liu, Fang Zhu, Dan Shen, Yawei Liu and Min Wang, "Omni-directional cylindrical patch array antenna using liquid crystal polymer technology," *2014 IEEE International Conference on Communication Problem-solving*, Beijing, 2014, pp. 269-272.
- [12] Chen Bing-jie and Hu Da-cheng, "Circular polarization microstrip antenna array with compact structure for anticollision radar," *2014 IEEE International Conference on Communication Problem-solving*, Beijing, 2014, pp. 91-94.
- [13] P. M. Anju, A. O. Lindo, C. K. Aanandan, D. D. Krishna and P. R. Young, "Novel Millimeter-Wave Antenna Array Using Half Mode Substrate Integrated Waveguide (HMSIW)," *2012 International Conference on Advances in Computing and Communications*, Cochin, Kerala, 2012, pp. 274-277.
- [14] Zhong-xiang Zhang, Ming-gang Fu and Chang Chen, "A 24GHz microstrip array antenna," *Proceedings of 2011 International Conference on Computer Science and Network Technology*, Harbin, 2011, pp. 214-217.